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GEOMORPHOLOGICAL STRUCTURE OF THE LESSER CAUCASUS

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Abstract: *The article discusses the relief forms and types common in the Lesser Caucasus, as well as their distribution over the territory. The Lesser Caucasus is an important morphostructural unit of the South Caucasus. Tectonic movements, volcanism and denudation-accumulation processes played a role in the formation of its relief. The main morphostructures common in the Lesser Caucasus include Murovdag, Shahdag, Karabakh ridge, East Goycha, Karabakh volcanic plateau, Shamkir massif, etc. The relief of the Lesser Caucasus is not characterized by a single watershed, but has a block-step structure. In terms of sea sculpture, accumulative-denudation, fluvial, karst and glacial relief forms are widespread in the area. Canyons, river valleys, terraces, karst caves, volcanic cones, and glacial traces located here complicate the relief. B.A. Antonov, Kh.K. Tanrıverdiyev, N.Sh. Shirinov and others played an important role in studying the relief of the area. The Dashalti Canyon belongs to the fluvial relief forms, the Azikh and Avey caves to the karst relief, and the Bashkend-Dastafur depression to the accumulative relief.*

Keywords: *Geomorphological structure, morphostructure, morphosculpture, tectonic structure, accumulation*

The Lesser Caucasus Mountains are generally located in the Lesser Caucasus Uplift. Only the eastern and southeastern parts of this uplift are located within Azerbaijan. The Lesser Caucasus Mountains continue in the direction of the Greater Caucasus from northwest to southeast in Azerbaijan. The mountain range enters the country's territory in the west through the Khram River valley. The most important relief units of the Lesser Caucasus Mountains within Azerbaijan are the Shahdag, Murovdag, Sharqi Goycha, Karabakh, Zangezur, Darelayaz ranges and the Karabakh volcanic and Yazi plateaus. This mountain range and the Karabakh volcanic plateau occupy 29% of the territory of our republic in total. The total area of the Lesser Caucasus Mountains in Azerbaijan is approximately 25 thousand sq. km. The Lesser Caucasus Mountains do not form mountains located parallel to each other. The Azerbaijani part of the mountain system is formed from the Shahdag and Murovdag ranges in the north and their mid-mountainous northern slopes. To the west of the Akhinchay basin, there are inter-river transverse ridges of the Lesser Caucasus with a height of 1000-1200 m (Uchgul-814; Shishdag-1084 m; Chanlibel-1121 m, etc.). The Shahdag range, one of the main orographic units of the Lesser Caucasus, extends 50 km eastward from the source of the Akhinchay. The important peaks of the Shahdag range are Gojadag-3318 m; Hinaldag-3367 m. The Murovdag range extends 55 km eastward as its orographic continuation. The Murovdag range includes Gamishdag with a height of 3724 m; Murovdag with a height of 3340 m and Goshgar-3368 peaks. The Lesser Caucasus, one of the important morphostructural units of the South Caucasus, is characterized by its unique lithological composition and complex geodynamics. Tectonic structure, volcanism, and long-term denudation-accumulation processes have played a role in the formation of relief forms in the area.

The location of the Lesser Caucasus Mountains, located in the central segment of the Crimean-Caucasus, in the Alpine-Himalayan orogenic belt and the diversity of morphogenesis processes occurring here have led to the complexity of the relief. All morphostructures and morphosculptures of the Alpine-Himalayan orogenic belt are found here.

Morphostructure

The southeastern part of the Lesser Caucasus in Azerbaijan includes the Shahdag, Murovdag,

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Karabakh, Mykhtoken, Murguz, Eastern Goycha ranges, the Karabakh Volcanic Plateau, the Shamkir massif, as well as a number of mountains and depressions. In addition to the main mountain ranges, there are also smaller ranges, ridges, plateaus, elevations, and depressions in this area.

The convex (high) relief part extends mainly from the northwest to the southeast and descends towards the Kura depression. Shahdag and the Karagüney and Murovdag ranges located northwest of it extend in a northwest direction. The Murovdag range is one of the highest parts of the region. The Mikhtoken range extends in a curved form towards the south. The Karabakh range is mainly located in a northwest direction and its different parts continue in different directions. The East Goycha Range is located south of the Shahdag Range and extends in a meridional (north-south) direction.

One of the largest relief units of the Lesser Caucasus is the Karabakh volcanic plateau. This plateau covers a large area in the upper reaches of the Hakari and Tartar rivers. The area narrows as it extends from the northwest to the southeast. The plateau is mainly formed by lava and volcanic debris, and there are many volcanic cones here. The highest point is Dalidagh (3616).

The Shamkir massif, which consists of low and medium-altitude mountain formations extending in various directions, is surrounded by the Ganja-Gazakh inclined plain in the northeast, the Ganja River valley in the southeast, the Bashkend-Dastafur depression in the southwest, and the Tovuz River valley in the northwest. There are also volcanic heights, plateaus, ridges and depressions.

Figure 1. Geomorphological map of the Lesser Caucasus

Morphosculpture

Fluvial landforms: The tributaries of the Kura and Araz rivers flowing through this area have divided the Lesser Caucasus with deep valleys. In the middle mountainous area, wide canyons have been carved in the Mesozoic limestone rocks. Such canyons include the Dashalti canyon, and the left tributaries of the Ganjachay near Dastafur have created wide canyons. According to research, the oldest river valley was the upper reaches of the Agstafchay, the Tartarchay and Bashkend-Dastafur, an ancient valley running parallel to the Khachbulag depression.

Karst landforms: In the Lesser Caucasus, karst relief is mainly distributed in the limestone and

gypsum rocks of the Cretaceous period in the northeastern and southeastern parts. Surface karsts are mainly found in the areas of Fizuli, Aghdara, Gazakh region, Aveydagh, Goranboy, etc. Covered karst formations are found on the Shusha plateau, in Askeran and Jabrayil regions (around the villages of Salatakin, Azikh, and Tugh).

Accumulative and accumulative-denudational landforms: Since the area is mainly mountainous, accumulative landforms are not as widespread here. Accumulative landforms include alluvial and alluvial-proalluvial landforms. They are widespread in closed intermountain depressions. These landforms are found in the Khankendi, Bashkend-Dastafur, Umudlu, and Khankendi depressions and consist of extensive accumulative terraces.

Accumulative-denudational landforms occupy a wider area in the Hakari River basin. The Gubadli plateau, which occupies a large area in the southeast of the Lesser Caucasus, is also an accumulative-denudational plateau.

Glacial landforms: Traces of ancient glaciers are found in the Lesser Caucasus, the reason for this is that well-preserved glacial landforms are observed mainly in high mountainous areas. Modern glaciers are not found in the southeastern part. The most widespread glacial landforms in the region are karsts, cirques, trog valleys, and partly moraine piles.

Conclusion. The morphogenesis processes taking place in the Lesser Caucasus are characterized by the complex morphostructure of the terrain. The tectonic movements and volcanic activity taking place here, along with the processes taking place over a long period, have created morphostructures. Groundwater, fluvial, glacial and accumulative processes have played an important role in the formation of morphosculptures. The region has a block-step structure endogenous.

Geomorphological regions of the Lesser Caucasus	
Shahdag-Murovdag	Hekari
Eastern-Goycha Range	Gazakh-Aghdam
Karabakh Volcanic Plateau	Khojavand-jabrail
Tartar	Asgulum-Zangilan
Dashkan-Gadabay	Khankendi

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